

EMPOWERING WOMEN'S COFFEE HARVESTING GROUPS IN UTILIZING COFFEE SKIN WASTE INTO PRODUCTS WITH ECONOMIC VALUE IN BENER MERIAH REGENCY

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Abstract

Currently, most coffee processing is limited to the use of coffee beans. Coffee waste production accounts for approximately 72% of the weight of the fresh fruit and has not been optimally utilised. In Bener Meriah Regency, women engage in harvesting activities as a means of generating income for their families. With the formation of this group, it is hoped that this group of women harvesters will not only carry out harvesting activities but can utilize unused coffee skin waste and can be used to create items of high economic value. This community service activity will be carried out in Kenine Village, Timang Gajah District, Bener Meriah Regency. The target output to be achieved is increasing partner awareness to become entrepreneurs and have the skills to produce products such as tea, fertiliser and fish pellets from coffee skin waste.

Keywords: *Coffee Skin, Women, Coffee, Income*

INTRODUCTION

Aceh Province contributes approximately 10% of Indonesia's total coffee production, making it a key coffee production centre (Hartatri & Sulaiman, 2018). Aceh is Indonesia's largest Arabica coffee producer, reaching 66,550 tons in 2020, with production spread across two districts. The two largest coffee-producing districts in Aceh Province are located in the Gayo Plains: Central Aceh Regency and Bener Meriah Regency (Pusdatin Kementan, 2023), known for their Gayo Coffee. Currently, most coffee processing is limited to the use of coffee beans. Coffee waste accounts for 72% of the weight of the fresh coffee beans and has not been optimally utilised. Generally, coffee waste is simply placed on the ground to be composted. However, in some areas of Indonesia, coffee waste becomes a breeding ground for pests and diseases (Ma'alhunah & Hendrawan, 2019). Timang Gajah District, one of the largest coffee-producing districts in Bener Meriah Regency, consists of 10 villages, including Kenine Village. Based on the results of the pre-survey conducted, the village head stated that traditionally, coffee harvesting activities are carried out in groups by women who are paid based on a contract system of Rp. 30,000 per can, where each can is equal to 14 kg, and this work is seasonal because the coffee harvest has a different harvest season. The women who carry out this harvesting activity as an effort to meet family income, and they harvest on several coffee owners' land. The harvested coffee is then ground by the coffee land owner to separate the skin from the beans. This women's harvesting group usually numbers around 10-15 people from the same village, but has not been officially established and is only voluntary. When not harvesting activities, usually the women from this group not only care for children at home, but some also look after the stall. Therefore, from this pre-survey, it can be

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seen that partners do not have the motivation to carry out entrepreneurial activities other than as harvesters, besides not knowing the potential to manage the abundant coffee skin waste. This is due, in part, to the inherited mindset that women are solely coffee harvesters and the limited resources and infrastructure needed to develop their skills and expertise. Therefore, during the pre-survey, a simple women's coffee harvesting group, chaired by Mrs Aprilia, was formed. With the formation of this group, it is hoped that the women's coffee harvesting group will not only engage in harvesting activities but will also be able to utilise unused coffee husk waste and create products with high economic value. This will help increase income. Therefore, training is needed for women harvesting groups to process this coffee husk waste. The objectives of this activity, based on the Higher Education Standards (KPI), include developing coffee husk waste processing technology to reduce pollution and producing processed coffee husk waste products to increase community income. This objective relates to KPI 5, which requires the use of lecturers' work by the community. The objectives of this activity to be achieved are, the emergence and development of an entrepreneurial spirit, have the expertise and skills to be able to produce products of economic value by using coffee skin waste and the formation of micro-scale economic business institutions with business management and marketing skills

METHOD

The following are the forms of partner participation in the PKM activities that will be implemented: Table 1.

Forms of partner participation in PKM activities

Stages	Manager	Partners
Analysis	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Providing information related to the learning process and the availability of infrastructure 2. Actively involved in FGD activities 	Participate in socialization and observations regarding partner characteristics, independence and skills
Design	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Together with the team, design extension and training methods for community service activities according to the characteristics of the partners. 2. Create and test pre-test and post-test evaluations for each activity session. 	
Development	Conduct outreach, counseling and training to partners in accordance with the timetable that has been prepared.	Partners participated in socialization, outreach and training activities with a participation rate of 100%.
Implementation	Provide assistance to partners so that they can produce according to the standards that have been conveyed in counseling and training.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Partners can make products independently according to the standards that have been provided and trained. 2. Partners can prepare institutional administrative requirements
Evaluation	Providing input to partners regarding several obstacles in both production and business management	

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The evaluation results will be used as a basis for the sustainability of program activities for women coffee harvester groups. It is hoped that women coffee harvester groups that have established micro-enterprises can then collaborate well with other institutions such as the Department of Industry and Trade and the Department of Agriculture to develop and sustain their businesses. This will also contribute to the sustainability of mentoring in other activities, such as thematic KKN (Community Service Program) activities, and ongoing research by lecturers and students, which can contribute to the community, particularly women coffee harvester groups.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the activities that have been carried out, the results of the implementation obtained are:

Table 2. Results of Activity Implementation

No	Problems	Solution	Output Target	Completion Target
1	Not having entrepreneurial motivation and making coffee picking a way of life	Training I: Entrepreneurial motivation counseling	The emergence of entrepreneurial motivation, thus encouraging partners to become entrepreneurs and recognize business opportunities by utilizing waste.	The results of the activities obtained after conducting the Pre-Test and Post-Test showed that there was an increase in partner motivation to become entrepreneurs in an effort to increase income by 92%.
		Training II: Counseling on the use of coffee skin waste		
2	Do not have the skills to produce products of economic value	Training III: Training on making compost from coffee skin waste	The development of partner expertise to produce products that have economic value and are in demand in the market by utilizing available coffee skin waste.	The results of the activities obtained after conducting the Pre-Test and Post-Test showed that there was an increase in the skills of partners to produce products with economic value of 93%.
		Training IV: Cascara tea making training		
		Training V: Training on making fish feed from		

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		coffee skin waste		<p style="text-align: center;">Skill</p> <p style="text-align: center;">PreTest: 18 PostTest: 93</p> <p style="text-align: center;">PreTest PostTest</p>
3	Do not have online-based business and marketing managerial skills	<p>Training VI: Socialization of the formation and requirements for establishing micro businesses</p> <p>Training VII: Micro-business management</p> <p>Training VIII: Digital marketing socialization and training</p>	The emergence of awareness to establish a micro-business-based economic business unit and the development of digital-based business and marketing managerial capabilities.	From the activities that have been carried out, the partner group has established an organizational structure called the "Blessed Women's Business Group", which currently has 12 members, who have plans to be able to produce other products according to the expertise of each member.

Based on the results of the activities, it can be concluded that

1. There is an increase in public awareness in good environmental management and utilizing coffee skin waste as a product of economic value.
2. Partners can now produce products from coffee skin waste
3. Partners have established a good organizational structure.

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